

Metabolomics as Glue of Integrative Omics

**Optima™ MAX-XP
ultracentrifuge**

UHPLC – Vanquish™/Orbitrap Fusion™

Attune™ NxT

Milli-Q™

**High-resolution
confocal microscope**

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Targeted Metabolomics

- Low number of metabolites studied
- Identity of metabolites known
- Absolute quantification of metabolites

Untargeted Metabolomics

- The whole complements of metabolites studied
- Identity of most metabolites unknown
- Relative quantification of metabolites

Metabolomics analysis applications

- Laboratory and natural yeast metabolomics
- Metabolic reprogramming of cancer cell lines/tissues
- Metabolic markers identification in liquid biopsies
- Food and Animal metabolome profiling
- Environmental metabolomics

Untargeted Metabolomics Analysis Workflow

Tandem Mass Spectrometry to acquire more structural information (MS² or more MSⁿ)

Sample Preparation

Data Acquisition

Data Processing

Small molecule
annotation

Metabolomics and
Transcriptomics/Proteomics
profiles integration

Statistical Analysis

Metabolomics data analysis and integration

ELIXIR Metabolomics Community

F2F meetings:

- 18th Annual Conference of the Metabolomics Society, Valencia (ES), June 19-23, 2022
- ELIXIR All-hands Meeting, Dublin (IE), June 5-9, 2023 (<https://f1000research.com/documents/12-1379>)
- Heidelberg (DE), October 16-17, 2023

ELIXIR Staff Exchange Project Italy-Greece (February-July 2024) IBIOM/FORTH

Standardizing the reconstruction of the **YE**ast **ME**tabolic **NE**twork through integration of multi-omic datasets and comparative genomics (**YEAMENE**)

IBIOM/UNIFI collaboration within AI-Health & Life Science PhD project

Creation and curation of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (and fungi) Metabolomics database for the integration with yeast Genomics, Transcriptomics/Proteomics and Metagenomics data in a Systems Biology perspective.

ELIXIR-IT
AHM
2023

CNR-IBIOM
Istituto di Biomembrane, Bioenergetica
e Biotecnologie Molecolari

CNR.BiOmics
BIG DATA FOR BETTER LIFE

nextGenIT
Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

1st ELIXIR-IT Workshop on Metabolomics

**Metabolomics and
Integrative omics:**
from data production to analysis

28-29 Aprile 2022 | BARI

Future

Aims of Community:

- Create and extend metabolomics datasets
- Develop data analysis workflow for metabolomics
- Promote data standards and interoperability in metabolomics
- Support computing with large-scale metabolomics data
- Increase the metabolomics training available

Creation of the Italian metabolomics community